

DEVELOPMENT OF STRENGTH QUALITIES IN ROWERS

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ABSTRACT

Rowing as a sport requires a high level of strength, endurance, and coordination abilities. This thesis scientifically substantiates the factors, methods, and stages of developing strength qualities in athletes engaged in rowing.

Rowing is a sport that requires a high level of physical and functional preparedness, in which the athlete is required to harmoniously demonstrate such complex qualities as strength, endurance, speed, balance, coordination, and mental endurance. In particular, strength quality is one of the main factors determining the speed of the rower's movement in the water, the amplitude and rhythm of rowing, as well as the effectiveness of the entire crew's work. Lack of strength leads to a disruption of stability in the athlete's technical movements, acceleration of fatigue during competition, and, as a result, a decrease in overall effectiveness.

During rowing, the athlete demonstrates high muscle strength to overcome water resistance. Therefore, the development of strength qualities contributes not only to increasing muscle mass, but also to performing movements technically correctly, rhythmically, and effectively. Strength training involves not only the muscles of the arms, shoulders, and back, but also the central muscle groups that ensure synchronous movement of the entire body.

The purpose of the research is to develop a training methodology aimed at developing the strength qualities of rowers and to determine its effectiveness.

The object of the research is the process of physical training of rowers.

The subject of the research is a system of special exercises aimed at developing the strength qualities of rowers.

Research methods The study used methods of analysis of scientific literature, pedagogical observation, testing, experimental classes, and statistical analysis.

Main Part In rowing, strength qualities occupy a leading place among the main physical qualities. This quality allows the athlete to overcome water resistance with each stroke of the oar, increase the speed of the boat, and maintain technical stability. Strength quality is closely related to the speed of muscle contraction, their energy production capacity, and the perfection of movement coordination.

In the development of strength qualities, the correspondence between general and special strength training is of great importance.

- General strength training is aimed at developing all muscle groups of the athlete, which prepares the athlete's body for complex physical loads.

- Special strength training consists of exercises similar to rowing movements, which improve the purposeful functioning of muscles.

General strength training includes:

- exercises with a barbell, dumbbell, stone, or simulator;
- exercises performed using one's own body weight (pulling, squats, abdominal presses, etc.);

- static strength exercises (exercises for maintaining muscle tension for a certain period).

Special strength exercises are divided into the following types:

- performing resistance exercises on a rowing machine;
- repetition of rowing movements with weight or elastic rubber bands;
- short-distance high-speed water rowing (to increase maximum explosive force).

In the training process, it is important to correctly distribute the volume and intensity of the load. For example, it is recommended to perform strength exercises 2-3 times during weekly training sessions, perform 4-6 types of exercises in each session with a set of 2-4 repetitions. Loads should be adapted to the athlete's level of preparedness, age, and recovery capabilities.

Studies show that in rowers engaged in strength exercises, maximum strength indicators increased by 15-25%, the ability of muscles to quickly contract improved, and the level of coordination of movements increased. In this case, exercises for developing the strength of the back, shoulder, arm, and abdominal muscles have yielded particularly effective results.

When performing strength exercises, the athlete's technique, rhythm of breathing, and coordination of muscle activity should be under control. Excessive loads can lead to muscle fatigue and overstrain. Therefore, when performing strength exercises, it is important to gradually increase the load, correctly organize the processes of rest and recovery.

Moreover, strength exercises yield more effective results when developed in combination with other physical qualities - endurance, speed, and coordination. For example, by combining strength and endurance, an athlete has the opportunity to maintain a stable expenditure of strength at long distances, which serves to show high results in competitions.

Thus, the correct organization of training for the development of strength qualities of rowers significantly increases the athlete's technical skills, speed of movement in the water, and competitive preparedness.

Conclusion The development of strength qualities of young rowers is one of the important factors in improving their sports skills. Strength quality is crucial for overcoming water resistance during rowing, performing technical movements accurately and effectively, and maintaining stable results throughout the competition.

The conducted analyses show that the organization of training sessions for the development of strength qualities on a scientific basis, the selection of exercises

corresponding to age and the level of training, ensures high effectiveness. The combined use of general and special strength exercises leads to coordinated work of muscle groups, improvement of movement amplitude and rhythm.

Also, proper planning of strength exercises - individual determination of the volume of loads, rest intervals, and training intensity - allows for a stable increase in strength indicators without harming the athlete's health.

The results confirm that the development of strength qualities in rowers significantly improves not only the level of physical fitness, but also technical skills, coordination of movements, and competitive stability.

Therefore, the introduction of a system of special strength training into the training process in rowing, the development of a program of step-by-step strength loads for young athletes, and their practical application is an important methodological direction for further improvement of sports results.

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